

APPLICATION OF BFRP CRACK PATCHING TO MIRAGE III AIRCRAFT

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This paper describes some work leading to the recent application of BFRP Crack-Patching to the field repair of fatigue-cracks in the aluminium alloy wing-skins of Mirage III aircraft. Aspects covered include finite-element design procedures, fatigue-crack propagation studies on patched panels, simulating the cracked and repaired area, materials and process selection, and the development of a Crack-Patching Field-support Unit. Repairs are currently being carried out by specially trained RAAF personnel during routine maintenance of the aircraft.

INTRODUCTION

ARL (Australia) has pioneered the use of adhesively bonded boron-fibre reinforced plastic (BFRP) patches to repair cracks in aircraft components. This procedure has been successfully used in several applications on RAAF aircraft, including the field repair of stress-corrosion cracks in the wings of Hercules aircraft and fatigue-cracks in the landing wheels of Macchi aircraft (1,2). Repairs were made by adhesively bonding the BFRP patch to the component with the fibres spanning the crack; the aim was to restrict opening of the crack under load, thereby reducing stress-intensity and thus preventing further crack propagation. Adhesive bonding provides efficient load transfer into the patch from the cracked component and eliminates the need for the additional fastener holes (which introduce dangers such as fretting) associated with conventional mechanical repair procedures. The advantages of using BFRP for the patch material include high directional stiffness (which enables reinforcement only in desired directions), good resistance to damage by cyclic loading and corrosion, and excellent formability. Both BFRP and CFRP have the above advantages for use as patch materials, but BFRP was preferred for most practical applications because of its better combination of fatigue strength and stiffness and its higher expansion coefficient (which reduces the severity of residual stress on cooling following adhesive-curing at elevated temperature). The low electrical conductivity of BFRP is also a very important advantage since conventional eddy-current procedures can then be used to detect and monitor cracks beneath the patch.

Recently, fatigue cracks were discovered in the lower wing skins, close to the main spar of some Australian Mirage aircraft, Figs. 1 and 2. It was decided, in consultation with RAAF, that BFRP crack-patching would be an effective solution for this problem, because the repair would (i) cause no mechanical damage to the skin (i.e. no fastener holes), (ii) cause no strain elevation in the spar, since reinforcement need only occur across the crack, (iii) allow the use of conventional eddy-current procedures to check for crack growth, and (iv) allow implementation in the field during normal servicing, thereby minimising unavailability of the aircraft. Because of the significance of the cracking and the long life desired of the repair, detailed design studies and a considerable amount of further research and development were required before the repair could be implemented. Some aspects of this work are reported here.

PATCH DESIGN AND ANALYSIS

The fatigue cracks initiated near the fuel decant hole in the lower wing skin, close to the intersection of the main spar and root rib (Fig. 1). The skin consists of aluminium alloy AU4G, similar to 2014T6, about 3.5 mm thick and is covered by a fairing. The wing skin Panel is in a state of shear which results in the fatigue cracks propagating at 45° to the spar (Fig. 2). For design purposes the maximum size of the crack (including the fuel decant hole) was taken as 111 mm. Flight loads were estimated from strain-gauge data from a wing fatigue test and from the manufacturer's stress analysis.

The BFRP patch (Fig. 2) is a unidirectional laminate with fibres running perpendicular to the direction of crack propagation. The patch contains seven layers of BFRP and is internally stepped, i.e. the largest layer is on the outside to reduce inter-laminar shear stresses. The proximity of the spar bolts and the root rib bolts to the decant hole necessitated closer spacing of the layer steps in this region. The attachment holes for the decant hole cover were preformed in the patch; the decant hole opening was much reduced in size by the patch, so as to obtain maximum reinforcement efficiency.

The main objectives of the analytical procedure were to assess the reduction in stress-intensity in the skin, reveal any undue strain elevation in the spar and to estimate the maximum levels of stress in the BFRP patch and adhesive layer. Ideally, a sufficient reduction in stress-intensity should be obtained without exceeding the materials allowables in the patch system, the most critical of which is the adhesive shear strength under fatigue loading in the operating environment.

FIG. 1. Silhouette of Mirage III aircraft showing where the fatigue cracks developed in some aircraft.
 INSERT: Fuel decant hole region, showing the nature of the fatigue cracking.

FIG. 2. Schematic diagram of fuel decant hole region with outline of BFRP patch superimposed; note the internal stepping of the patch.

Finite Element Analysis

Initially, a detailed finite-element stress analysis of the cracked region was undertaken using standard procedures. The resulting stress-intensity factors, assuming loads typical of a 6g flight manoeuvre were $K_1 = 57 \text{ MPa } \sqrt{\text{m}}$, $K_2 = 3 \text{ MPa } \sqrt{\text{m}}$ at the tip nearest to the spar, and $K_1 = 54 \text{ MPa } \sqrt{\text{m}}$, $K_2 = 1 \text{ MPa } \sqrt{\text{m}}$ at the tip nearest to the root rib.

The effect of the patch was estimated by adding a finite-element representation of the BFRP patch to the crack model (Fig. 3) utilizing a special element described in (3); this model allows for the separate response of the wing skin, patch and adhesive. In the specific case when the xy axis system coincides with the axis of orthotropy of the patch, the relationships between displacements and shear stresses in the adhesive layer reduce to:

$$\tau_{zx} = (u_o - u_s) / (t_a / G_a + 3t_s / 8G_s + 3t_o / 8G_{13})$$

$$\tau_{zy} = (v_o - v_s) / (t_a / G_a + 3t_s / 8G_s + 3t_o / 8G_{23})$$

which is similar to the relationship developed in (4). Here τ_{zx} and τ_{zy} are the shear stresses developed in the adhesive; t_a , t_s and t_o are the thicknesses of the adhesive, wing-skin and patch respectively; (u_o, v_o) and (u_s, v_s) are the x,y displacements in the wing-skin and the patch; G_s and G_a are the shear moduli of the skin and the adhesive respectively, and G_{13} and G_{23} are the transverse shear moduli of the patch.

Several patch adhesive thickness combinations were considered each with the same plan form shown in Figs. 2 and 3. Finally, from the results of the analysis a seven-layer patch was chosen, maximum thickness about 0.89 mm, with an adhesive layer 0.2 mm thick. For this patch, the stress-intensity factor (K_1) was reduced

FIG. 3. Finite-element mesh for the fuel decant hole region.

by at least 90% and the fibre strains were well below the maximum working level of 0.005 (equivalent to a stress of 1000 MPa, assuming a composite modulus of 200 GPa). The shear stresses in the adhesive were (Fig. 2):

Point A	14 MPa	at edge of patch
Point B	24 MPa	at edge of patch
Point C	51 MPa	at edge of decant hole
Point D	41 MPa	at edge of decant hole.

At locations C and D, the shear stress in the adhesive could cause localised fatigue damage (5) but more detailed analysis showed that this damage was only very localised and that small areas of debond in this region should not adversely affect the patch efficiency.

The effect of the patch on the maximum principal stress in the skin along the line of attachment to the spar (Fig. 4) showed that the patch effectively restores the stress distribution along the spar to that in a wing with an uncracked panel. Consideration was also given to thermal and residual stress effects in the aluminium skin and to thermal-fatigue effects in the adhesive due to the use of an adhesive curing at elevated temperature ($\sim 120^{\circ}\text{C}$) and the mismatch in thermal expansion between the aluminium alloy and BFRP. It was concluded (6,7,8) that these effects posed no serious problems in this particular repair.

FIG. 4. Stress distribution in the aluminium skin. The curves are for the stress, σ , for ratios between three cases denoted by subscripts; p = patched and cracked, u - unpatched and uncracked, and c = cracked and unpatched.

REPAIR QUALIFICATION

The BFRP repair was qualified mainly by two series of tests (a) a strain survey on a Mirage wing with a patch installed to show that the patch did not significantly elevate the local strain in the spar, and (b) fatigue tests on aluminium alloy panels configured to simulate the cracked area in the wing (Fig. 5). The aims of the fatigue test were to check that (i) the predicted reduction in stress-intensity could be achieved, and (ii) the patch/adhesive system could endure the fatigue loading. The strain survey confirmed that no significant strain elevation occurs in the spar after patching. The fatigue results are given below.

Fatigue Crack Propagation Studies

Tension-tension fatigue tests were undertaken on the aluminium alloy panels using either constant load cycling or block load cycling. Only the principal tensile stress in the wing could be simulated. The tests were carried out in a laboratory environment at a temperature of 23°C. Tests under more realistic environmental conditions are planned. Initially, due to unavailability of 2014T6 material, tests were carried out on aluminium alloy 2024T3 panels. Although this alloy has significantly greater resistance to crack propagation than the wing skin alloy AU4G, it was considered that these tests would show whether or not the stress-intensity was reduced by patching and if the fatigue characteristics of the adhesive layer were satisfactory. Cracks were initiated from saw-cuts and propagated to about 100 mm total length prior to BFRP patching, using the procedures described below. During application of the patch, the panels were constrained at their ends to simulate the constraint to thermal expansion that would be experienced in the wing-skin under practical repair conditions. This rate of crack growth was monitored during the initial test by direct observation with a travelling vernier microscope. After patching, eddy-current procedures were used to monitor the crack under the patch.

FIG. 5. Details of 2024T3 aluminium alloy wing-skin simulation panels used for crack-propagation studies, showing position of patch and vacuum box restraint.

In the early tests local bending of patched panels occurred under load due to local displacement of the neutral axis of the panel by the patch. This effect negated the reinforcing effect of the patch to a large extent. Strain-gauge tests confirmed the presence of substantial strains in the panel on the opposite side to the patch. In the actual wing-skin, local stiffening by the surrounding structure, particularly the spar, root rib and internal stiffeners, would largely prevent bending and a method was therefore devised to minimise its occurrence in the test. This procedure used atmospheric pressure to hold the panel against a relatively stiff, flat honeycomb sandwich panel (by evacuating the region between the back of the test panel and the sandwich panel). A thin layer of porous, fluorocarbon-coated fibre-glass between the test panel and the sandwich panel acts to allow air removal in the gap between the test panel and sandwich panel and minimised the frictional load. Strain-gauge studies showed that the bending effects were then reduced by about 50%.

Using the vacuum restraint, substantial increases in life prior to crack growth were achieved; Fig. 6 plots crack growth curves for three 2024T3 specimens subjected to constant load cycling at an applied stress of 91 MPa, (equivalent to a nominal 4g manoeuvre load). In all cases initial crack growth rates indicated that failure of the panels (without the repair) would have occurred within a further 10^4 cycles.

Panels were tested under more realistic loading conditions using a block-loading sequence adapted from the Mirage load spectrum previously developed at ARL. Each program sequence is approximately equivalent to one year of aircraft usage. Substantial life extensions for the cracked 2024T3 alloy panels, (Fig. 7) indicate that, provided local bending is minimised, the BFRP patch system provides a significant stress-intensity reduction. The actual life extension probably depends largely on the degree to which local bending is reduced in practice.

The long life of the repair indicates that the patch/adhesive system is capable of withstanding sustained fatigue loading, at least in a laboratory environment. Currently tests are being conducted using panels of 2014T6 alloy, the material used in the aircraft wing skin. These panels are prepared with the rolling direction oriented similarly to that in the wing skin. Tests to date show that cracks propagate in these panels very much faster than in 2024T3; the results for one such panel are included in Fig. 7. It is worth noting that the notched 2014T6 panels could not withstand one complete program of the loading sequence; crack growth to the 'repair size' occurred at load level 5 (~ 5g), whereas the loading sequence goes to load level 9 (~ 9g). This observation suggests that the stressing level employed in these tests may be higher than that encountered by this region in the aircraft, since, in practice, cracks are not found to grow this rapidly.

SELECTION OF MATERIALS AND PROCESSES

Adhesive

An epoxy-nitrile structural adhesive, 3 M's AF126, was chosen on the basis of previous background studies into suitable adhesives for crack patching, which included work on fatigue and stress relaxation (5), and practical experience on repairs to stress corrosion cracks in Hercules aircraft over a period of more than four years (2). AF126 cures at about 120°C and requires a pressure of 70-350 kPa. Originally, an adhesive curing at a lower temperature and pressure was sought to simplify patch application and minimise thermal and residual stress problems. Unfortunately, none of those studied were suitable; future development of a suitable adhesive curing at lower temperatures and pressures would greatly aid patching technology.

Surface Treatment

In previous repairs, non-chemical surface-treatments of the aluminium alloy component were used to simplify patch application procedures and to avoid the danger of stress-corrosion cracking. This treatment was degreasing, followed by

FIG. 6. Crack length versus cycles for 2024T3 wing-skin simulation panels subjected to constant load cycling; stress intensity range prior to patching is indicated.

FIG. 7. Crack length versus number of programmes of block loading for 2024T3 and 2014T6 wing-skin simulation panels.

grit-blasting with 50 μ m alumina powder; the same procedure was used for preparing the BFRP patch. However, it was considered that the present repair required a higher level of environmental durability than would be provided by this procedure, because of the critical nature of the cracking and the long life required of the repair. It was decided therefore, to evaluate the phosphoric acid gel anodising procedure recently developed by the Boeing Aircraft Co, for field repairs to adhesively bonded aluminium components (9). Table 1 lists details of the solution used and the anodising conditions. Boeing wedge tests were used to compare the

Acid Gel:	Orthophosphoric acid	
	AR grade 88%	0.15 l
	Distilled water	to 2.0 l
	Aerosil 200	0.240 kg
Voltage required		0-6 volts
Rate of change of voltage		1 volt steps at 1 min. intervals
Time at 6 volts		10 min.
Total anodising time		15 min.

Table 1. Materials and Conditions for Surface Anodising (Boeing process)

effectiveness of various surface-treatments, including alumina grit-blasting, gel anodising, and standard tank anodising (factory procedure). The results (Fig. 8) show that gel anodising gives adequate durability. Although the use of primer gave further improvement, its application was considered too difficult to control under field conditions. Prior to final acceptance of the gel anodising procedure, further wedge tests showed the bond to be resistant to fuel immersion, the main environmental contaminant in the present repair. Other tests showed that the gel anodise procedure did not cause stress-corrosion cracking in the 2014T6 material.

FIG. 8. Crack length versus time in hours (log scale) for Boeing wedge test specimens bonded with adhesive AF126, after various pre-bonding surface treatments; schematic diagram of a wedge specimen is shown above.

Patch Manufacture

Patches were manufactured from pre-preg tape obtained from Composite Technology Inc as type 4.0/296 impregnated with 3 M's PR-286 epoxy. The tape was initially cut into plies by a numerically controlled laser which also made the cut-outs for the bolts of the decant assembly and the fuel drain opening. The plies were then assembled on a jig, using the bolt holes as datum points, and were consolidated in a heated platten press. Vacuum was applied during heat up prior to gellation; the vacuum was vented to atmosphere and pressure applied via a silicone rubber pad. Patches were produced in batches of 8, Fig. 9 shows a typical batch of patches, encapsulated in peel ply, together with quality control specimens. It is of interest to note the wash of boron particles around the lower quality control specimen, Fig. 9, which was prepared by mechanical cutting of the BFRP pre-preg and compare this with the clean edges produced by laser cutting. The quality control specimens were used to determine interlaminar shear strength and void content.

FIG. 9. Batch of finished BFRP patches and quality control specimens encased in peel ply material.

Environmental Protection

In addition to the use of the phosphoric acid gel anodise procedure a number of other measures were taken to improve the durability of the patch system. Contact of the bond surface of the patch with fuel was minimised by bonding an aluminium plug into the decant hole with polysulphide rubber (PR1422) prior to application of the patch. The edges of the patch and adhesive bond were then sealed by bonding an aluminium tube through the hole in the aluminium plug and patch. Finally, to prevent contact of the outer surface of the patch with moisture, aluminium foil was bonded over the BFRP patch using polysulphide rubber.

Patch Removal Procedure

A method for removing installed patches was developed to allow replacement of incorrectly applied or out of life patches. Patch removal is accomplished by use of a proprietary epoxy disintegration solution ("Decap" produced by Dynaloy Inc) which is heated to a temperature of about 120°C and sprayed against the surface of the patch, using either a paddle wheel or a pump to provide the spray. Using this procedure a patch can be removed in less than 24 hours with no chemical or mechanical damage to the wing.

REPAIR IMPLEMENTATION

Patch Application

Application of BFRP patches to the Mirage wings under field conditions during routine aircraft servicing required the development of several techniques, the design and construction of a 'Crack-Patching Unit' (CPU) and the development of specialised training procedures for RAAF technical personnel. The CPU (Figs. 10 and 11) contains all the equipment necessary for making the repair, including a grit-blaster and anodising unit for surface-treating the skin, and temperature controllers and hydraulic pressure indicators for controlling the skin heating and patch pressurisation systems during the adhesive cure.

Detailed operating procedures for the CPU and the patch application were prepared; Fig. 12 indicates the various steps employed in the patching procedure. The turn around time per aircraft is about 3 days or about 4.5 man days per wing. A finished patch, complete with aluminium foil environmental protection coating is shown in Fig. 13.

The main problems in developing the system were to obtain uniform heating of the wing-skin and pressurisation of the patch system. The phosphoric acid gel anodising of the underside of the wing posed no particular problems, provided gel of sufficient consistency was used; however rigorous quality control was essential to ensure that the surface was uniformly and correctly anodised. A considerable amount of effort was required to devise methods which would achieve uniform heating of the local area of the wing; the main problems were the proximity of the massive spar which acted as a heat sink and which was not allowed to exceed 100°C. Other workers (10) had shown that exposure to temperatures above 100°C could result in loss of residual stress (cold work) around fastener holes with a consequent reduction in cycles to fatigue crack initiation. The maximum allowable temperature in the skin was 135°C to minimise overaging effects, and the minimum 110°C to ensure cure of the adhesive in the required time. During heating trials, a dummy patch with an array of thermocouples bonded into the pre-cured adhesive layer was used to estimate the temperature distribution. The method finally adopted was to heat the area with three independently controlled heaters situated along the spar and root-rib and over the skin region; the last also acted as a caul plate for the hydraulic ram (Fig. 11).

The danger of damaging the skin during pressurisation of the patch at temperature was reduced by limiting the pressure to 140 kPa. Uniform pressure over the patch region was obtained by using a silicon rubber pad, moulded to accept the patch, under the caul plate; a thin metal frame was incorporated into the rubber to prevent pressure loss at the edges of the patch. The efficiency of the pressurisation and heating procedure was assessed by examining the adhesive for voids, flow and cure in tests where the adhesive layer was separated from the surface of the wing and patch by a fluorocarbon film during cure.

Quality Control and NDI

Periodic checks on adhesive flow and cure are carried out (as above) by the repair team to ensure correct operation of the heating and pressurisation system. The surface-treatment procedure is checked by manufacture of wedge-test specimens

FIG. 10. Crack Patching Unit (right) and equipment chest (left) under Mirage wing; grit-blast container box can be seen in the background.

FIG. 11. Hydraulic system in place supporting the heater system during cure of the adhesive.

FIG. 12. Sequence of steps involved in the patch application procedure.

FIG. 13. Finished BFRP patch, complete with external environmental protection in position on a Mirage wing.

during a repair operation. The adhesive sheet prepared during the flow test and the wedge-test specimens are returned to ARL for evaluation.

During patching, quality control of the surface-treatment process is carried out by observing water break during drying and examining the anodised surface under polarised light (at a low angle of incidence) which shows up the continuity and quality of the anodised layer. Finally the degree of flow of the adhesive around the edges of the patch (flash) is examined and the degree of cure estimated by a simple pencil hardness test on the flash.

NDI of the wing prior to patching is performed using a simple eddy-current procedure and the position of the crack noted. After patching, a more sophisticated, low frequency, eddy-current procedure is used to detect the crack below the patch. The thin aluminium foil (environmental protection) layer on the patch does not interfere with this NDI procedure.

DISCUSSION AND CONCLUSIONS

BFRP crack-patching to repair fatigue cracks in the lower wing skin of Mirage aircraft is still in its early stages so that definite claims for its success cannot be made. Short-term laboratory tests cannot yet resolve uncertainties about long-term environmental degradation of adhesive bonds. Further, the precise nature of the stress in this region of the wing, particularly the degree of bending, is not fully known and no allowance was made for biaxial effects, due to the transverse compressive stress, which could promote local displacement of the crack faces. However, it has been shown that BFRP crack-patching is highly cost-effective and that it can lessen aircraft unavailability because it can be successfully applied under quite difficult field conditions by specially trained service personnel with no previous experience of structural adhesive bonding. The advantages of crack-patching over conventional repair procedures are: (a) no mechanical damage to surrounding structure, no fastener holes, (b) crack can be inspected through the patch by conventional eddy-current NDI, (c) the cracked area is protected from further external corrosion, and internal fuel leakage, by the patch system, (d) reinforcement is only in the direction required, no undesirable stiffening in other directions, and (e) patches can be removed and replaced with no damage to the surrounding structure.

Although development of the CPU and repair procedure involved considerable effort at ARL, most of this work will not be repeated in further repairs, although changes may be required to the heaters and pressurisation systems. With the addition of a vacuum pump (for which provision has been made), the CPU could be used for general crack-patching, repairs to adhesively bonded metallic components, repairs to fibre composite components and for general repair of battle damage.

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